

Virtual Mobility Grant (VMG)

Roadmap on reanalysis of long-term, multivariate time series based on ReOBS and other methods for future implementation on networks

Full report

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Key messages :

- Today, many applications such as climate variability studies, process understanding, numerical model evaluation (global or regional) and satellite mission assessments require to access data sets comprising long-term series of high-quality, standardized, harmonized, and spatially and temporally homogeneous measurements.
- Several European and worldwide observation networks, facilitated by data centres, collect high-quality data on atmospheric physico-chemical processes from the surface to the upper troposphere, spanning through the boundary layer.
- Despite their potential, these databases remain under-exploited. Conducting multi-year, multi-variable, and multi-site studies to understand variabilities and their representativeness poses challenges for users due to several reasons:
 - The completeness of datasets as initially described may be compromised, with missing files, periods, or variables.
 - File formats might vary over time (e.g., NetCDF, ASCII).
 - Inconsistent (pre-)processing of variables/products over time.
 - Inadequate control of data quality within files (e.g., outliers from level 0 data).
 - Heterogeneous nomenclatures and metadata over time.
- Tools/products like ReOBS or ARMBE can homogenize and standardize these data, ensuring a high level of quality control to create a multi-parameter dataset easily usable by the scientific community. These tools feed directly into the various data centres of the observation networks mentioned above.
- Given the complexity of processed data, these tools are typically multifunctional. They enable assessment of databases managed by data centres but cannot replace them entirely. Instead, they assist in ensuring complete, consistent, and high-quality data over time.
- The initial datasets harmonized through ARMBE and ReOBS show promising potential for end-users, resolving previously identified issues. Scaling these valuable datasets across extensive network sites requires significant efforts in automating and adapting configurations and quality controls. However, these tools are hindered by limited methods to address missing data, automatically detect anomalies, or correct biases. In this context, with abundant data from various observation networks, artificial intelligence (AI) presents new avenues for reconstructing long-term, homogeneous, and high-quality datasets.

1 – Introduction

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) simulations exhibit a considerable divergence among models in forecasting future global climate, as well as in replicating the observed current climate. These uncertainties are more pronounced at regional scales and shorter timescales (e.g., seasonal scale), which are crucial for impact assessment. Notably, models struggle to accurately depict inter-annual and seasonal variability and extremes in temperature and precipitation. Incorporating atmospheric observations is essential for enhancing our understanding of the processes underlying temporal variability and simulation uncertainties. These observations should encompass a wide array of atmospheric variables across different spatial and temporal scales.

Multi-annual and multi-variable datasets from ground-based observations are invaluable resources, offering comprehensive and precise information spanning several decades. Despite their scientific significance, data from observation networks are underutilized, particularly in harnessing observed synergy due to complexities in calibration procedures, quality control, data treatment, and temporal representativeness.

Integrating atmospheric observations from ground-based observatories can enhance our understanding of climate processes and improve the accuracy of climate simulations. However, leveraging these observations effectively requires addressing technical challenges and comprehending the complex interactions between local-scale processes and broader climatic phenomena.

In addition, it is imperative for satellite measurements to have access to datasets of high quality controlled that are both spatially and temporally consistent. These datasets play a vital role in calibrating and validating satellite measurements accurately. Unfortunately, these data sets are either lacking or too limited in number. Note that at the opposite the space research community already worked on homogenized and reanalysed products that have recently been released (e.g.

<https://climate.esa.int/en/about-us-new/climate-change-initiative/>,
https://www.cmsaf.eu/EN/Highlights/Dokumente/News_15.html).

2 – Available tools and requirements

An important homogenization work is thus needed for these observations (section 2a). There are two main type of methods available today for the research community to robustly process ground-based data at an hourly timescale over more than a decade (sections 2 b-c).

a) Requirements

There are requirements to be followed by the different instrumented sites that would like to obtain a multi-parameter dataset with a high level of quality control (data and metadata).

About the data (if not already in data centres [i.e. level 0]):

- The data must be directly measured geophysical quantities or derived from algorithms. In the latter case, it is necessary to provide the references of the algorithms used.
- If they exist, it is necessary to provide additional information such as quality flags on the context of the measurement (the instrument, the observation, breakdown period, drift...), other control parameters or any information having an influence on the data or the measurement. It is also important to mention if the instrument has been subject to a technological upgrade over the years.
- Input files can be in text format (ASCII, CSV...) or NetCDF.
- The filename should be different for all files.
- It is important to have no temporal overlap within and between the different files.
- Timestamp should be in UTC.

- No time drift is recoverable (the acquisition system must be synchronized to a time server).
- Source files can be daily, monthly or yearly.
- The altitude of the measurements must be temporally homogeneous and in meters Above Ground Level.
- The database must remain accessible in order to guarantee the reconstitution of the data set at any time.

About global metadata :

- Write station name and/or its respective ID
- Name of the institution where the file was created (ACTRIS, BSRN, GRUAN, ...).
- GPS coordinates of the measuring station latitude and longitude in DMS (degrees, minutes, seconds).
- Altitude of the station, and altitude of the instruments in relation to the ground in meters.
- Membership (if any) of the measurement in a national or international network.

Examples of both global and variable attributes are given in Figures 1-2.

P R O B E C O S T A C T I O N

```
[attrs]
title = SIRTA ReOBS meteoairsol_air dataset
summary = The 20-year-long SIRTA-ReOBS dataset is contained in a single netCDF file
containing mean values of more than 150 physical variables. Variables entering the ReOBS
dataset are quality controlled at their native time resolution. The objective of ReObs
is also to respect the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)
in particular the Reusable aspect which is more obvious for a production chain.
keywords = GCMD: ATMOSPHERE,GCMD: AEROSOLS,GCMD: AIR QUALITY,GCMD: ATMOSPHERIC
PRESSURE,GCMD: LAND SURFACE/AGRICULTURE INDICATORS,GCMD: ATMOSPHERIC RADIATION,GCMD:
ATMOSPHERIC TEMPERATURE,GCMD: ATMOSPHERIC WATER VAPOR,GCMD: ATMOSPHERIC WINDS,GCMD:
CLOUDS,GCMD: PRECIPITATION,GCMD: DATA ANALYSIS AND VISUALIZATION,GCMD:
CALIBRATION/VALIDATION,GCMD: DATA ANALYSIS,GCMD: STATISTICAL APPLICATIONS
keywords_vocabulary = GCMD
Conventions = CF-1.7, ACDD-1.3, ISO 8601
naming_authority = AERIS data center
source = AERIS data center,ACTRIS-FR,SIRTA,Meteo-France
comment = Technical and scientific staff of SIRTA site discuss with AERIS data center
staff to develop the quality check and provide the metadata information concerning
variables and instruments.
acknowledgement = The ReOBS database is maintained by the French national center for
Atmospheric data and services AERIS. We extend our acknowledgments to the technical and
computer staff of SIRTA Observatory for taking the observations and making the data set
easily accessible.We also thanks the ACTRIS-FR Research Infrastructure for their support
in this study.
license = Inspired by CC-BY
standard_name_vocabulary = CF Standard Name Table v76
creator_name = AERIS data center
creator_type = Data center
creator_url = https://www.aeris-data.fr/
institution = AERIS data center
project = AERIS data center,ReOBS
program = ACTRIS-FR
references = https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-10-919
2018,https://doi.org/10.1002/2014GL060205,https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-012-1469-
y,https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-00329353
publisher_name = AERIS data center
publisher_type = Institution
publisher_url = https://www.aeris-data.fr/
processing_level = See ATBD
metadata_link = https://reobs.aeris-data.fr/
```

Figure 1 : Example of typical global attributes associated with the final file.

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```
[ta]
long_name = Air temperature
standard_name = air_temperature
units = Celsius
instrument = guilcor_pt100(20140101-now)
comment = sensor installed at 2m agl inside no ventilated shelter
coverage_content_type = physicalMeasurement
```

Figure 2 : Exemple of typical variables attributes associated with the final file.

Note that these data homogenization and standardization tools are at the end of the data lifecycle chain. In fact, these tools are designed to feed directly into the various existing data centres (ACTRIS, BSRN, GRUAN, AERONET, etc.), providing direct, easy access to all data from Levels 0 to 2 (L0-L2). Databases remain sometimes heterogeneous due to software and instrumental changes, presenting significant potential if homogenized and standardized. This means that all files must use the same version of the processes applied, and that there must be no legacy files. Tools such as ReOBS and ARMBE (see section 2b, 2c) can provide valuable feedback to data centres on one of these issues, but should never be used as a substitute.

b) ReOBS

The prefix "Re" of ReOBS denotes six principal steps for ground-based observations: calibration, quality control, algorithmic processing, hourly averaging, standardization of data formats and metadata, and expert scientific analysis.

The ReOBS project (<https://reobs.aeris-data.fr/en/welcome/>) aims to produce a multi-parameter dataset with rigorous quality control measures, formatted for easy utilization by the scientific community in studying and comprehending regional climate variables. It seeks to aggregate, analyse, and standardize all observations, such as those from an ACTRIS National Facility or other, into a single NetCDF file with hourly time resolution (Figure 1). The ReOBS file is designed to adhere closely to CF and GCMD conventions for metadata, as well as the FAIR principles.

PROBE COST ACTION

The ReOBS tool:

1. Adapts to the raw input data provided by ground-based observations sites.
2. Implements advanced quality control procedures to identify and eliminate erroneous data, as documented in an ATBD available upon request.
3. Conducts temporal and/or spatial averaging of the data.
4. Generates a comprehensive, merged, and well-documented NetCDF file.

Figure 1 : ReOBS a new approach to synthesize long-term multi-variable dataset.

c) ARM-BE

In the same vein as ReOBS, and having begun few years earlier, the equivalent product developed in the USA is called ARMBE for Atmospheric Radiation Measurements Best Estimate.

The ARMBE data product, formerly known as the Climate Modeling Best Estimate (CMBE), consolidates essential cloud, radiation, atmospheric, and surface/land property data from ARM instruments into a single dataset (Acquerman et al 2003; Xie et al., 2010). Aimed at fostering increased utilization of ARM data in climate research and model development (<https://www.arm.gov/>), ARMBE offers a comprehensive collection of well-observed quantities commonly utilized in model evaluation. For more than twenty

years, ARM ground-based instruments such as cloud radars, micropulse lidars (MPLs), laser ceilometers, microwave radiometers (MWRs), and solar and infrared radiation stations (SIRs) have measured these quantities. Specifically designed for climate modelers, ARMBE features hourly temporal resolution akin to typical climate model output, including standard deviations within averaged hours and quality control flags to indicate data variability and quality.

ARMBE's detailed observations of clouds and their broader atmospheric context across various climate regimes contribute significantly to process studies aimed at enhancing cloud parameterization in climate models. Moreover, its long-term dataset with high temporal and vertical resolutions facilitates the examination of climate variability, change, and the statistical evaluation of climate models. ARMBE also serves as input for several ARM value-added products (VAPs), such as ARM Diagnostics for Climate Model Evaluation (ADCME) and large-scale forcing data from constrained variational analysis (VARANAL).

Comprising two components, ARMBEATM and ARMBECLDRAD, ARMBE provides essential atmospheric data and detailed cloud and radiation quantities, respectively. However, it's important to note that ARMBE represents single-point measurements, necessitating statistical methods for comparison with climate model outputs, which often represent grid-box means over 100 kilometres. Despite stringent quality control measures, ARMBE still encounters data quality issues inherent in the VAPs used to generate it, including Active Remote Sensing of Clouds (ARSCL), Data Quality Assessment for ARM Radiation Data (QCRAD), and Microwave Radiometer Retrievals (MWRRET).

3 – Existing datasets across the European ecosystem

The two methods presented above are flexible enough to adapt to different datasets. In view of the issues raised in the introduction to this document, a number of observation

networks could easily benefit from the added value of these tools. Here we make a review of some of Europe's or world's high-potential networks.

a) ACTRIS

The Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure (ACTRIS) is a pan-European research infrastructure (RI) that generates high-quality data and information concerning short-lived atmospheric constituents and the processes influencing their variability in both natural and controlled environments (<https://www.actris.eu/>).

The atmosphere operates through intricate chemical and physical mechanisms, and accurate predictions rely on sophisticated models grounded in observational data. ACTRIS plays a crucial role in refining emission source uncertainties, understanding deposition processes, and quantifying their ecological impacts. It also contributes vital insights into global biogeochemical interactions and climate-ecosystem feedback loops. Additionally, ACTRIS aids in identifying sources of air pollutants affecting human health and complements Earth Observations from space, providing essential ground-truthing for satellite data.

ACTRIS offers access to high-quality atmospheric data and advanced facilities. It develops technologies for climate and air quality modelling, benefiting diverse users in research, space agencies, and more. ACTRIS fosters community integration to achieve common goals and meet user needs efficiently.

Currently, ACTRIS consists of 22 countries, 112 national facilities, and 6 topical centers, which the latter serve as essential operational entities within this research infrastructure. These centers play a crucial role by offering services to users in line with ACTRIS access policies, providing operational support to National Facilities to enhance their performance, and contributing to ACTRIS governance and management.

P R O B E C O S T A C T I O N

Figure 2 : World and Europe maps of the various ACTRIS National Facilities, respectively.

b) BSRN

The Baseline Surface Radiation Network (BSRN) serves as the central archive for radiation measurements, accompanied by surface and upper-air meteorological observations and station metadata. BSRN (<https://bsrn.awi.de/>), a project of the Global Energy and Water Exchange (GEWEX), aims to detect changes in Earth's radiation field related to climate change. Its data are vital for validating satellite and computer model estimates. With stations in various climatic zones, BSRN measures solar and atmospheric radiation with high accuracy and time resolution (Figure 3). In 2022, BSRN renewed its commitment to Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) activities and was recognized as a GCOS network for global surface radiation measurements.

Figure 3 : BSRN stations in 2022. The symbols on the map indicate the status of BSRN stations: green stars for those that have submitted data, yellow squares for stations with delayed data submission, red triangles for closed stations, and white dots for provisional BSRN sites awaiting data submission.

c) GRUAN

The Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) Reference Upper-Air Network (GRUAN) is an international network of sites dedicated to measuring essential climate variables above the Earth's surface (<https://www.gruan.org/>). It addresses a crucial gap in the global observing system by providing long-term, high-quality climate data from the surface to the stratosphere. These measurements are utilized to analyse trends, validate data from other observing systems like satellites and radiosonde networks, and investigate atmospheric processes. GRUAN aims to expand to 30-40 sites globally, leveraging existing observational networks and capabilities where feasible (Figure 4).

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d) AERONET

The AERONET (AERosol ROBotic NETwork) program, established by NASA and LOA-PHOTONS (CNRS), along with various networks and collaborators, has provided a comprehensive database of aerosol properties for over 25 years. This database supports aerosol research, satellite retrieval validation, and synergizes with other databases. AERONET (<https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/> and Figure 5) ensures instrument standardization, calibration, and data processing. It offers globally distributed observations of spectral aerosol optical depth (AOD), inversion products, and precipitable water in different aerosol conditions, categorized into three data quality levels: Level 1.0 (unscreened), Level 1.5 (cloud-screened and quality-controlled), and Level 2.0 (quality-assured).

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C ● S T

A C T I ● N

Figure 5 : Map of active AERONET measuring stations in 2023.

4 – Results and potential applications

The ARMBE product has already been used in 54 publications since the creation of its first dataset, which continues to grow year after year. For instance, Zheng et al. 2023 demonstrated the usefulness of having a long-term, homogeneous and standardized dataset of very high quality to assess the performance of climate models in reproducing simulated clouds and surface short-wave radiation.

Ground-based observations from six Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) user facility sites are used to statistically assess the performance of cloud and radiation simulations in climate models from the Coupled Model Inter-comparison Project Phase 5 (CMIP5) and their successors in Phase 6 (CMIP6), originating from 10 different modelling institutes. The study reveals model biases in simulating clouds and radiation and identifies improvements and degradation in model performance from CMIP5 to CMIP6. Insights into parametrization issues and physical processes aid in future climate model development (Figure 6).

Similarly, Cheruy et al. (2013) emphasizes the importance of evaluating land-atmosphere interactions in climate models to mitigate uncertainty, presenting a new method to assess boundary layer, convection, and cloud parametrizations within the Earth System Model (ESM) developed by the Institut Pierre Simon Laplace (IPSL). The study examines two different land surface hydrology parametrizations and compares

ten-year simulations of the coupled land surface/atmospheric ESM modules with observations from a ReOBS-SIRTA (Site Instrumental de Recherche par Télédétection Atmosphérique (Haeffelin et al. 2005) - which is an ACTRIS National Facility) near Paris (<https://sirta.ipsl.fr/>). By refining the model grid and adjusting the large-scale circulation, the study identifies areas where parametrizations perform poorly and affect regional climate simulations. It highlights factors contributing to biases in near-surface variables and demonstrates how new parametrizations can improve model performance.

Another example, small-scale processes such as surface–atmosphere interactions and cloud feedbacks are considered crucial for understanding near-surface temperature variations (Chiriaco et al., 2014). ReOBS-SIRTA facilitates this understanding by providing a multi-variable synergistic compilation, allowing for the study and comparison of various atmospheric or surface characteristics (Bastin et al., 2018). Building on this foundation, Rojas et al. (2021) further explore the specific impact of clouds on local 1-hour surface temperature variations in the Paris region, utilizing the comprehensive dataset provided by ReOBS-SIRTA.

Finally, a first intercomparison of the evolution of aerosol optical thickness in Europe was carried out on 3 ACTRIS sites (Granada [Spain], Lindenberg [Germany], and SIRTA [France]) thanks to the synergy of 3 different ReOBS (Figure 7). Assuming that optical thickness is directly linked to air quality and PM10 concentration (as a proxy), we can see that the same trends are found at the various European sites. A general decrease in aerosol optical thickness is thus observed, confirming the overall improvement in air quality across Europe in recent decades.

Figure 7: Seasonal evolution of aerosol optical thickness at 675nm at Granada (top), Lindenberg (center), and SIRTA sites (bottom).

5 - Conclusions and future-directions

As discussed in this document, standardized, homogeneous, and high-quality datasets are crucial for linking with climate and regional models or for evaluating space missions.

ARMBE (ARM Best Estimate) and ReOBS are projects/tools that provide standardized datasets with hourly temporal resolution, incorporating quality control measures, and adhering to metadata conventions, catering to the needs of the scientific community for evaluating global and regional climate models and enhancing climate research efforts. These initiatives meet the expectations for standardized, accessible data to advance climate studies and model development. Note that in a context where carbon footprint monitoring associated with new measurement (and campaigns) is gaining in importance, these tools enable both measurements and results from recent decades to be reinterpreted, making them easier to use and promoting instrumental synergy.

The ReOBS approach outlined in this paper is being extended to other super-sites. Presently, efforts are being made to apply this approach to data from national facilities within the ACTRIS infrastructure, particularly the Lindenberg site in Germany (with over 100 years of measurements) and the Granada site in southern Spain. Additionally, discussions are ongoing regarding the application of ReOBS to other ACTRIS national facilities. Other ongoing initiatives include integrating the ReOBS dataset into the OBS4MIP (Observations for Model Intercomparisons Project) database, dedicated to comparing observational data with CMIP simulations.

Also, new collaborative effort between the USA and Europe, known as CARGO-ACT, is set to commence in spring 2024. This collaboration aims to bring together the ARMBE and ReOBS tools, showcasing the strength of these high-quality datasets for the research community through joint synergies at various sites worldwide (ARM and ACTRIS). This collaboration is expected to materialize in the coming months.

Despite the immense value of these datasets produced by ARMBE or ReOBS tools, effectively scaling them across vast networks of sites demands substantial efforts in automating and customizing configurations and quality controls. Ensuring consistency and accuracy across diverse sources and environments is a challenge. Existing tools face limitations in addressing critical issues such as missing data, anomalies detection, and bias correction, which can impede the reliability and usefulness of the datasets. Missing data necessitates robust imputation techniques to fill gaps without introducing biases. Anomaly detection demands sophisticated algorithms to distinguish irregularities from noise, helping in flagging significant events or errors. Bias correction requires tailored methodologies to maintain dataset integrity by adjusting for systematic errors, ensuring the accuracy of analyses and predictions. With abundant data from those observation networks, artificial intelligence (AI) presents new avenues for enhancing data quality and utility. Leveraging AI can help revolutionize data quality assurance, enabling more accurate analyses on various atmospheric fields.

5 - References

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